

The Role of Green Human Resource Management Practices in Enhancing Hybrid Work Teams Field Research at Federal Public Service Council

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Abstract

Hybrid work has emerged as a significant force in today's organizations. Despite its significant momentum in contemporary organizations, as it combines traditional and non-traditional work by relying on shift work, it remains a vague concept that lacks a clear definition. Therefore, our research paper seeks to bridge the gap that has not been addressed by researchers regarding the most influential elements of hybrid work teams by presenting a comprehensive and precise concept based on our review of the scientific literature. Hybrid work teams have become an urgent need for organizations after the major lockdowns caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, as they have provided unexpected opportunities for employees to experience working from home (off-site).

Therefore, this study aims to understand the role played by green human resource management practices in strengthening hybrid work teams. The research adopted the descriptive-analytical approach, as a purposive sample was selected, including a group of 40 officials and employees of the Federal Public Service Council, to answer the questions of the questionnaire designed for this purpose. The results showed a direct, positive, and significant correlation between green human resource management practices and hybrid work teams among the Council's officials and employees. Meanwhile, the green performance evaluation dimension had the greatest impact in strengthening hybrid work teams, as it enables employees to feel that their efforts are respected and appreciated by the Council's senior management.

Keywords: *Green human resource management practices, hybrid work teams, Federal Public Service Council.*

JEL Classification codes: *J28, O15.*

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Introduction

In recent years, organizations have adopted more conscious strategies and programs to enhance integration between human resource management and the environment. Consequently, interest in the concept of green human resource management has grown, given its significant role in promoting compliance with environmental management standards through the implementation of environmentally friendly activities in the areas of recruitment and hiring, performance evaluation, training, compensation and rewards management, and in line with sustainable development goals. At the same time, organizations have begun to rely on hybrid work teams, which combine the specific work styles of employees in offices and remotely, enhancing diversity and flexibility within the organization. Here, the role of green human resource management emerges as an important tool for meeting the requirements of this type of team, as it aims to reduce their presence in the organization by encouraging them to carry out some of their activities in person, while completing other tasks remotely. This contributes to reducing carbon pollution and achieving environmental sustainability.

The term "hybrid" appeared in the context of work within organizations long before the pandemic. This was achieved through the creation of hybrid workspaces as a result of the growing interest in working from home due to workers' remote locations, as well as the increased reliance on virtual work due to the increasing pressure on offices (Smite et al., 2022:1). A study (Koglin et al., 2025) indicated that after the pandemic and with the gradual return to face-to-face work, many organizations preferred to maintain the hybrid model implemented during the pandemic, given the significant benefits it brought to both the organization and employees. However, as (Handke et al., 2024) indicated, individuals and teams face many challenges in hybrid work, including balancing the need for individual autonomy with difficulties such as coordinating dispersed team members or dealing with delayed communication between them (Manole et al., 2025:1). Therefore, most research on hybrid work teams has sought to create a sense of harmony between these teams to enhance their work performance. Leadership therefore plays the largest role in influencing these teams. A study by (Yozi & Mbokota., 2024) showed that organizations operating under a hybrid work model relied heavily on their managers to ensure its successful implementation. But what does an organization's leadership rely on to enhance the performance of its hybrid work teams?

The **main research problem** lies in shedding light on the existing gap between hybrid work teams and the organization's leadership by identifying what the organization's leadership will rely on to enhance the performance of its hybrid teams and achieve organizational sustainability. After reviewing numerous studies, green human resource management practices were identified as one of the most important elements upon which organizations rely to support and enhance the performance of their teams. Therefore, the research gap lies in understanding the role of green human resource management practices in enhancing hybrid work teams.

The Federal Public Service Council was selected as a research field, as it relies heavily on traditional and hybrid work patterns to complete its work in receiving and verifying data from applicants seeking employment. The research was divided into four sections. The first section addressed the theoretical framework of the research, highlighting the concept of green human resource management practices, hybrid work teams, and their dimensions. The second section addressed the practical framework of the research, while the third section discussed the results. Finally, the fourth section addressed the conclusions reached by the research.

Theoretical Framework

Green Human Resource Management Practices:

The world around us is increasingly concerned with environmental issues and sustainability in general. Green practices have become an important focus in organizations' work to achieve the environmental dimension, which has become a fundamental pillar of the current century, in conjunction with the emergence of artificial intelligence, hybrid teams, and remote work. Despite its relative novelty, Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) has the potential to enhance positive environmental outcomes. Many organizations are now adopting conscious strategies to align with environmental standards, due to growing environmental concerns and international standards applied to preserve them (Perez, 2025:2). The growing interest in environmental sustainability and social responsibility has prompted organizations to adopt alternative approaches to fulfilling their responsibilities. This enables them to address the needs of stakeholders, ensure a better and sustainable future for all, and achieve a balance between economic, social, and environmental development (Alketbi & Rice, 2024:1). The term (G-HRM) refers to the integration of human resource management (HRM) and green HR management with the environmental movement through their participation in the strategic implementation of HRM practices within the organization (Shah & Soomro, 2022:292). Green HRM practices are defined as all activities involved in the development, implementation, and ongoing maintenance of a system aimed at making an organization's employees environmentally friendly. These practices include recruitment, performance management and evaluation, training and development, wages, and rewards (Arulrajah et al., 2015:2). (Masood ,2018:356) defines them as a set of practices used by HR management to encourage the sustainable use of its resources within the organization to promote environmental protection, which increases employee morale and satisfaction. For our part, we define green human resource management as a set of practices and policies adopted by an organization to manage its employees in a way that enhances their concern for the environment, making it a priority in their work, and ultimately promoting and disseminating it to all parts of the organization.

Majeed & Khan (2019) view it as policies, practices, and systems aimed at making an organization's employees environmentally friendly for the benefit of individuals, society, the natural environment, and organizations. These policies include recruitment, selection, performance evaluation, and compensation. Training programs are designed in this way to create a workforce that understands and supports green behavior within the organization. Green human resource management practices, as defined by (Bahuguna et al.,2022:3), mean integrating green practices into human resource management functions such as recruitment, development, performance management, and compensation management, thereby enhancing organizational sustainability prospects. They rely on a combination of activities that help organizations reduce their consumption of energy, natural resources, and unnecessary waste by recruiting and training human capital, establishing an appropriate performance management system, and using compensation and rewards as incentives (Wang et al, 2024:411). Green human resource management practices create a balance between work and the environment. They also enhance performance and maintain a green vision within each employee, transforming ordinary employees into environmental employees who strive to achieve the organization's environmental goals and thus make a significant contribution to environmental sustainability (Arulrajah et al., 2015:2). That is, they work to enhance and maintain the green spirit within each employee in the organization, so that they make the maximum individual contribution in each of the four roles: environmental expert, environmental scientist, non-polluter, and inventor (Masood, 2018:356). They also work to bring about economic change by raising environmental efficiency while ensuring that the cost of exploiting natural resources is within the acceptable range in these practices. They place environmental responsibility within their work tasks and work to enhance the ability of their employees to develop positive behaviors with

their colleagues at work and provide new ideas and recommendations (Ardiza, 2021:14). They positively impact the organization's environmental performance through activities such as waste reduction and overall organizational efficiency, and they promote green behavior among employees to voluntarily improve the organization's performance (Jackson et al., 2011:106). For our part, we believe that green human resource management practices achieve a range of benefits at the organizational level and the environment as a whole. At the organizational level, they enhance the image they seek to project in the public eye, as well as increase their competitiveness by attracting employees who wish to work for environmentally friendly organizations. From an environmental perspective, they help organizations reduce the environmental impacts of traditional organizations by reducing paper use and limiting the negative phenomena associated with traditional organizations, in addition to their significant role in promoting environmental sustainability.

Masood (2018) also demonstrates that green human resource management practices seek to achieve the following benefits:

1. Protecting environmental aspects such as global warming and climate change, etc., to create a safe and healthy work environment.
2. Guiding, educating, and encouraging employees to perform their activities in an environmentally trustworthy manner.
3. Increasing and improving organizations' environmental performance.
4. Motivating employees to participate in organizations' environmental management activities and developing green capabilities.
5. Providing environmentally friendly products and processes and successfully managing organizations' environmental programs.

Dimensions of Green Human Resource Management Practices:

Researchers have addressed the concept of green human resource management practices in multiple dimensions. For this study, we agree with the studies cited by (Nejati et al., 2017), (Haldorai et al., 2022), and (Barinua et al., 2022), who based their studies of green human resource management practices on the dimensions represented by (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, and green compensation). The following is a detailed explanation of these dimensions as follows:

1. **Green recruitment:** Green recruitment is one of the most important stages of human resource management, requiring the recruitment and retention of potential candidates. Green human resources management seeks out environmentally friendly talent to attract them to work for the organization, then works to recruit them and develop their businesses under a green umbrella (Ahmed, et al., 2019: 11). Therefore, it focuses on recruiting individuals with high knowledge and behavioral skills associated with the organization's green environmental management system (Sakwa, 2018: 3). Through this process, the organization works to establish its position as an environmentally friendly employer, attracting environmentally responsible individuals and those with green visions and values, integrating them into a green organization's culture (Tsymbaliuk, et al., 2022: 1). Green recruitment is described as a paperless recruitment process that involves inviting job applicants via online means such as email, online application forms, or telephone, and conducting interviews via videoconference to minimize any environmental impact related to travel (Gupta, 2013: 32 & Gupta).
2. **Green training:** This is one of the important activities of green human resource management, which aims to prepare employees to acquire skills and understanding of environmental issues and work to protect them (Uddin, 2018:384). It focuses on building environmental awareness among organizational employees at all levels through environmental

learning, which can lead to a change in the attitudes and behavior of organizational members. This learning involves encouraging employees to recycle and training them on the proper use of workspaces and energy conservation (Majeed & Khan, 2019:1837). Organizations have recently realized the importance of green training practices in their organizational environment, as without it, it is difficult to achieve the organization's targeted environmental performance. Related practices include training on environmental safety, energy conservation, waste management, recycling, developing green personal skills, reducing long-distance business travel, and retraining employees who have lost their jobs in polluting industries (Arulrajah et al., 2015:8).

3. Green Performance Evaluation: Measuring an employee's green job performance is one of the key functions of green human resource management. Without this practice, no organization can guarantee realistic environmental performance in the long term. Therefore, an employee's green performance must be evaluated separately, or at least as part of the organization's performance evaluation system (Arulrajah, et al., 2015: 8). Green performance evaluation can be defined as setting green standards and evaluating employee performance against those standards (Arora & Kaul, 2020: 62). Performance evaluation reflects the extent to which employees engage in job behavior and achieve results related to green practices over a specific period of time (Ardiza, 2021: 14). Including green behaviors in the performance evaluation system can accelerate their adoption among employees because it ensures regular feedback to employees on their progress (Majeed & Khan, 2019: 1837). Therefore, a performance evaluation system can achieve success for the organization by linking the performance evaluation process to job descriptions with sustainable green goals and tasks (Uddin & Islam, 2015: 15).

4. Green compensation: This is a green human resource management practice through which employees are rewarded for their sustainable performance, serving the interests of the employees, the organization, and the environment. This process supports environmental management and contributes to the development of innovative products (Jabbour & Jabbour, 2014: 10). These rewards include tangible and intangible incentives, such as praise and letters of appreciation, which help motivate employees toward environmental improvements or the management of hazardous waste. Therefore, organizations must develop reward systems by employing incentives and disincentives to achieve desired behavior (Margaretha & Saragih, 2013: 3). Green compensation practices aim to motivate employees to work toward environmental goals, as these rewards influence sustainable behavior. In addition to financial incentives, employees should also be motivated by non-financial incentives, such as green tax incentives and green travel benefits (Shah, 2019: 4).

Hybrid Work Teams

The emergence of hybrid work teams dates back to the early 1970s, when the concept of telework was developed. This concept involves the use of information technology devices and office equipment as a means of organizing and performing work, with employees working outside the workplace for a significant portion of the time (Wontorczyk & Bohdan, 2022: 2). However, the idea of hybrid work, despite its existence, did not become widespread until the pandemic era. This form of work was implemented earlier, and was defined either by the employee's professional details (mainly knowledge-based professions such as IT specialists, lawyers, and others) or by what is known as telework (Wójcik & Magdalena, 2023: 54). Information and communications technology has developed significantly in recent years with the emergence of modern technologies, leading to the emergence of so-called virtual teams using information and communications technologies within work teams (Meluso & James, 2022: 5). The concept of work has undergone a new revolution worldwide as a result of the incredible growth witnessed by technology. Over the past decade, it has become clear to organizations that the global outlook on work would change. Before the pandemic, some organizations were already incorporating a hybrid work system into

their structures. Since 2015, there have been predictions of the future of work, predicting that some types of jobs will become unsuitable in the coming years (Iqbal et al., 2015:23).

Today, the concept of “hybrid work” is viewed by individuals and organizations as work characterized by flexibility in terms of position, place, and time, as the work is performed partially from the employer’s headquarters, home, or from any other location with the help of digital tools and platforms, as a means of work and communication (Vartiainen & Vanharanta, 2023: 1). The word “hybrid” means that social work is digital and physical at the same time (Pink & Laura: 2022: 415). It describes the employee’s ability to enjoy a certain level of independence and flexibility in the location where he performs his work tasks through his use of information and communication technology (Hopkins, & Anne: 2023: 2). The hybrid work arrangement is defined as an arrangement in which the employee is required to work on-site for part of the time and can work effectively remotely from an alternative location for the rest of his work time (Nava et al: 2021: 3). To distinguish between a traditional and hybrid work team, a traditional team usually consists of a group of individuals who work interconnectedly with the same task and common purpose, share the same goals, and are an integral part of the organizational context, which refers to working within the same organization and managing relationships across organizational boundaries. A hybrid team, on the other hand, is geographically dispersed and relies on communication technology (Hämäläinen: 2022: 34). We define hybrid work teams as "a work model and a means of accomplishing tasks toward a specific goal from different locations, shared by employees through the creation of work teams with flexibility in choosing work locations and schedules, depending on organizational culture and technological techniques."

This mixed or hybrid strategy provides employees with the flexibility to work from the office or another location (e.g., home, coffee shop, coworking space), etc. (Krajčík & Matuš: 2023: 2). Hybrid work offers numerous benefits to organizations, including giving employee's flexibility while simultaneously not feeling isolated compared to their peers who mostly work from home (Choudhury et al., 2024: 4). Forming a hybrid team also requires the development of software that enables some team members to work within the organization and others outside their designated workplace (Conboy et al. 2023: 27). Furthermore, there must be a high level of interdependence and coordination among team members and a high degree of self-organization (Krzywdzinski 2022: 8). It also requires mixed or hybrid collaboration to accomplish work within and outside of the organization (Nyktarakis, 2022: 16). In addition to employee autonomy, which is a key factor in the success of hybrid work teams (Wiatr & Beata, 2022: 8), it is also essential to provide electronic or remote leadership, which refers to situations in which the team leader does not meet with their team members. Communication and collaboration take place via technology (Lindholm, 2021: 15).

There are different classifications of hybrid work teams based on the proportion of in-person or virtual work. These include: (in-person work, work outside the office and in different locations such as field work teams, mixed light, which refers to decentralized virtual work, usually one day per week, and hybrid work, which occurs when employees have the option to work remotely for several days per week). However, the office remains the central workplace (Winkler, 2022: 8). There are also so-called hybrid innovation teams, which are entirely virtual teams formed within organizations that rely entirely on artificial intelligence to accomplish work (Bouschery & Frank, 2023: 139). The hybrid work team model is being implemented in various organizations, whether public or business, because it contributes to achieving organizational goals and improving work efficiency. However, public sector employees who do not have sufficient experience in working remotely, which necessitates the development of a culture that promotes effective communication and technology to support work teams in these environments (Agnér, 2023: 7).

Dimensions of Hybrid Work Teams

From the perspective of the individual and the organization, "hybrid work" is understood as work characterized by flexibility in terms of specific situations, times, and locations. Work is performed from the workplace, home, or elsewhere, with the help of digital tools available to employees within the organization (Vartiainen & Outi, 2023: 1). Knowing how to create hybrid teams is not easy, as in order to properly design hybrid work, we must consider two important axes: space and time (Gratton, 2021: 3). When discussing the dimensions that researchers have addressed for hybrid work teams, we note the multiplicity of these dimensions. For the purposes of this research, we relied on a study by (Larose & Saatçi, 2023), as (Larose & Saatçi, 2023: 44) stated that there are three dimensions of hybrid work teams: communication, trust, and team identity.

1. Communication: The hybrid nature of teams means we must forget about the unified communication system, and since some employees Whether they are in the office or at home, communication with each group will inevitably occur through different channels (Wiatr & Beata, 2022: 6). Encouraging communication is an important organizational goal because it is positively linked to business success. Communication is expressed in multiple terms (collaboration, interaction, and knowledge sharing) and aims to transfer information from one person to another that is meaningful to participants. Communication at work may be planned or unplanned (Appel, et al., 2022: 2). Communication influences social cohesion and trust among team members and has a significant impact on team effectiveness. It is more difficult to achieve in hybrid teams because communication via electronic media reduces the social cues that help build relationships (Gifford, 2022: 109).

2. Trust: Working from home makes monitoring employee behavior more difficult, which affects leaders' trust in them. Employees may also risk losing important or confidential information, having their information corrupted, or being exposed to online information theft while working remotely if the required safeguards are not in place (Trivedi & Nikhil, 2022: 33). There are concerns about information confidentiality, and some organizations lack a culture of guidelines and procedures for remote work (Vyas, 2022: 161). In other words, online groups have greater needs regarding trust, leadership, and communication. Researchers have argued that trust is one of the biggest challenges facing online groups. Furthermore, trust is critical to the performance of online groups and is essential for operation and collaboration among team members (Kahlow & Erin, 2020: 62).

3. Defining Team Identity: A particular challenge facing hybrid teams is defining team identity, which can be influenced by the combination of co-located and geographically dispersed members. Strengthening team identity and awareness is a challenging and time-consuming process for teams due to the limited cues that help categorize teams. This creates uncertainty, as the transition from in-person to remote work has not only reduced collaboration within teams but also diminished bonds and belonging to the organization (Larose & Saatçi, 2023:18). Here, the role of organizational management comes in to strengthen the identity of its teams by fostering communication among team members and encouraging them to communicate with each other to strengthen relationships, which positively impacts their interactions within the team.

Green HR Management Practices and Hybrid Work Teams

Green HR management practices are a crucial element in enhancing the management of traditional and hybrid work teams in general today, as they represent a decisive factor in determining the long-term work pattern of these teams to achieve business sustainability. In a study conducted by Ramachandran (2024: 1291), which highlighted the most important strategies and effective practices used by HR departments to enhance employee engagement in hybrid work environments, the study results indicated that organizational management must enhance flexible work

arrangements and foster a supportive virtual culture to maintain high levels of engagement, which enhances diversity and inclusion within the organization. These factors are vital for maintaining employee engagement and reducing turnover in a dynamic work environment. (Baroudi et al, 2023:6) also demonstrated in a study that linked human resource management practices that integrate green aspects into the workplace to positive effects on the performance of teams within them. More specifically, the results showed that green human resource management influences team performance in general through a green behavioral process, including green team behaviors both within and outside of their roles. Green human resource management plays an important role within organizations, through its use of human resource management policies to promote the sustainable use of its resources, enhancing environmental sustainability and generating employment opportunities. The hybrid work model and remote work are considered the future direction of organizational work culture (Bandal & Nimje, 2023:1).

Today's workplace is witnessing major transformations, most notably the emergence of hybrid work models, in which employees work differently from the traditional model (on-site and remotely). This transformation presents both opportunities and challenges for human resource departments within organizations. (Khan ,2024:35) demonstrated in his study how human resource practices have evolved to address these challenges and capitalize on the opportunities offered by hybrid work environments. The study identified several areas of focus in hybrid work environments, including designing recruitment and onboarding strategies, performance management, development, and employee relations to suit hybrid teams to achieve their goals. Therefore, the organization's management must rely more on green human resource management practices to enhance the performance of its hybrid work teams. This will enable them to be more capable of dealing with the major changes they face inside and outside the workplace, and to achieve their goals in a manner consistent with the sustainability they aspire to achieve. Green human resource management practices work to strengthen hybrid work teams by promoting digital sustainability within the workplace, in addition to their specific behavior of encouraging employees within these teams to adopt green behavior at work, which helps them be more flexible in carrying out their work remotely.

Practical Aspect

Sample and Research Population

To accurately define the study population, we had to study a group of organizations that follow more than one work method to carry out their daily work. This means they rely on the traditional method to carry out their work, in addition to carrying out a portion of their work remotely or through locations outside the organization's main office. After studying several organizations, the Federal Public Service Council was chosen as the location. The researchers then conducted a series of visits to the council to observe the nature of the work they perform on a daily basis, thus determining the nature of their work.

The council's management was then approached to obtain approval to conduct the study there. After obtaining approval, the council's own sample of officials and employees was identified. This sample comprised 40 employees, representing the study population. most employees within the council were selected to obtain diverse opinions reflecting the academic background and job position of each employee for the purpose of arriving at results that reflect the overall picture of its employees.

Scale Design

For research purposes, a questionnaire was used as the primary tool for collecting and analyzing the data obtained. It was designed to cover all research variables using a five-point Likert scale. The questionnaire was prepared based on the study by Haldorai et al. (2022) for the first variable (green human resource management practices). For the second variable (hybrid work teams), the scales of Saldana and Saatci (2023) were used. The questionnaire was sent to the sample members after consultation via email. This ensured that the nature of the research was consistent with the subject matter, which relies on hybrid work teams, as well as with the green practices that the research aimed to promote in order to reduce paper waste and achieve sustainability.

Research Hypotheses and Hypothetical Diagram

The research hypotheses shed light on the relationship between the two research variables, determining the nature of the relationship between the two variables and determining the validity of the research model for the study. The main research hypotheses were as follows:

The first main hypothesis (H0): There is no statistically significant correlation between green human resource management practices in its dimensions (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, green compensation) and hybrid work teams at Federal Public Service Council

The second main hypothesis (H0): There is no statistically significant correlation between green human resource management practices in its dimensions (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, green compensation) and hybrid work teams at Federal Public Service Council

A hypothetical model can be placed to depict the movement of the research variables through its theoretical aspect, as shown in Figure (1).

Figure 1. Hypothetical Model

Reliability Test Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha is one of the most important statistical testing measures. It was developed by Lee Cronbach to provide a measure of internal consistency for statistical tests. It is expressed mathematically as a number between 0 and 1.

A closer examination of the current research data presented in Table (1) reveals that the combined reliability coefficient value for the two research variables (green human resource management practices and hybrid work teams) reached approximately 0.943. This value is statistically very high, as it is higher than the statistical average. This indicates that the two research variables successfully passed the reliability test. The table also shows that the independent variable achieved a reliability coefficient value of approximately 0.898, indicating that the variable possesses a high statistical reliability coefficient. The dependent variable achieved a value of 0.917. This demonstrates that the two research variables individually successfully passed the reliability test.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test for the Questionnaire Variables

Study variables		Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient	Researcher's comment
Independent	Green HR Management Practices	0.989	The respondent variable items have strong reliability.
Respondent	Hybrid Work Teams	0.917	The respondent variable items have strong reliability.
Total Questionnaire Items		0.943	Very strong reliability exists across all questionnaire items.

Description of the Research Community

In order to understand the studied community well and to know what characteristics and features it has that made it the focus of researchers' interest and an important site for the purpose of conducting the study on it, we must shed light on a group of factors (personal, demographic and academic qualifications) that the members of the community carry, and for the purpose of this research, the sample studied consisted of (40) respondents who represented the leaders and employees of the Federal Public Service Council by relying on the method of the intentional sample that represented the entire community to be studied, and Table (2) shows a description of the sample as follows:

Table 2. Results of the Descriptive Analysis of the Identifying Information for the Research Sample (n=40)

Identification Information	Category	Number	Percentage %
Gender	Male	25	75 %
	Female	15	25%
total		40	100%
Age	Less than 30	11	27.5 %
	From 31 - 40	26	65 %
	From 41 - 50	3	7.5 %
total		40	100%
Academic achievement	Bachelor's	29	72.5 %
	Master's	8	20%
	Doctoral	3	7.5%
total		40	100%
Number of years of service	Less than 2 years	21	52.5%
	2 to 3	11	27.5%
	3 than more	8	20%
total		40	100%

From the data contained in Table No. (2), it becomes clear to us that the largest percentage of employees in the Council are males, as their number reached (25) while the number of females reached (15). It is natural to find this percentage in it because males and females prefer to work in the government sector more than other sectors, in addition to the fact that the organization being studied is characterized by effort and tiring work for long hours and late at night, so we find that most of its employees are males. Regarding the age group, we note that the age group (31-40) constituted the largest percentage of respondents, with (26) employees out of (40). This indicates that most of the Council's employees are from the slightly older, middle-aged age groups. This is a good impression that reflects the organization's keenness to employ young people to manage affairs. This is followed by the age group under (30), with (11) of them, who came in second place in terms of age group ranking. The age group (41-50) came in last place. With regard to the axis of educational attainment We find that the holders of a bachelor's degree had the largest part, as the number of holders of a bachelor's degree reached (29) out of (40) employees and officials, and the number of those holding a master's degree reached (8) person, while the number of those holding a doctoral was (3), and this is a very natural matter for the nature of the Council's work. Regarding the number of years of service, we find that people with less than two year of work years constituted the largest number of respondents, as their number reached (21) people, while individuals with 2 to 3 years of service came in second place with (11) employees, while individuals with 3 than more years of service came in last place with (8). Here we note the increase in the number of young groups working in the council, and this is a natural thing that reflects its strengths.

Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

In this section of the research, we will shed light on the description of the two research variables: green human resource management practices with their dimensions (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, and green compensation) and hybrid work teams with their dimensions (trust, communication, participation, implementation and influence, team belonging, and non-negotiable topics). This will be achieved by conducting a set of statistical analyses using statistical methods and tools such as the weighted mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, and relative importance. We will also examine the correlation and influence relationships between the research variables and their dimensions, using some statistical equations, including the simple linear regression equation.

Presentation and Analysis of the Dimensions of the Independent Variable, Green Human Resource Management Practices

Table 3 shows that the independent variable, green human resource management practices, which included four sub-dimensions, achieved a good response to all of its dimensions at the overall level. The weighted arithmetic mean value reached 3.91, which is statistically very good, as it is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic mean value of 3. The standard deviation value reached 0.81, which is a good value, as it is less than one. The coefficient of variation for the responses of the research sample reached 20.71 at the overall level of the variable, and the relative importance of the variable recorded a value of 78.11. These percentages, from a statistical perspective, reflect the clear interest of the sample members in the research (Federal Public Service Council) in all of the paragraphs of the independent variable (green human resource management practices). This was clearly reflected in their responses to the questionnaire paragraphs, and indicates the extent of their understanding of the questionnaire paragraphs. The following is an explanation of the results of each. After the dimensions of the variable.

Dimensions of the Variable (Green Human Resource Management Practices)

Upon closer examination of Table 3, we find that the dimension (Green Performance Evaluation), which ranked first in the ranking, achieved a mean of 3.96 on the overall level. This is a very good

value from a statistical standpoint, as it is higher than the hypothetical means of 3. It reflects the importance of this dimension to the Council's employees. This is demonstrated by the homogeneity of the sample's responses and their significant agreement on the importance of green performance evaluation in enhancing the performance of hybrid work teams in general. The standard deviation for the dimension in general was 0.82. Although this decrease is not significant, it is good and reflects good homogeneity in the sample's responses regarding the importance of this dimension. Meanwhile, the coefficient of variation was 20.78, and the relative importance recorded a value of 79.15. This indicates that the surveyed members of the Council are aware of the importance of performance evaluation, as it reflects the extent of their commitment to performing their job duties.

The dimension (green compensation) achieved second place in terms of ranking, as it achieved a good arithmetic mean of 3.91, while the value of the standard deviation of the dimension was 0.82, and the coefficient of variation for the total of this dimension recorded a value of 20.95, while the relative importance reached 78.17. The dimension (green training) came in third place, as its weighted arithmetic mean reached 3.89, while its standard deviation reached 0.77, and this value is good and indicates the presence of good homogeneity among the individuals of the researched sample when they answered the questions of this dimension, while the value of the coefficient of variation reached 19.87, and the relative importance of this dimension was 77.81. The green polarization came in last place in terms of ranking, as the dimension achieved a weighted arithmetic mean of 3.87, while the standard deviation value of the dimension was 0.89, which indicates the presence of good homogeneity among the sample of respondents when they answered the questionnaire paragraphs, while the value of the coefficient of variation reached 21.24 and the relative importance recorded a value of 77.32.

Table 3. The Weighted Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation, Coefficient of Variation, and Relative Importance of the Green Human Resource Management Practices Variable and Its Dimensions

Independent Variable Green HR Practices	Mean	St. dev.	Coefficient of Variation	Relative Importance
Green Recruitment	3.87	0.82	21.24	77.32
Green Training	3.89	0.77	19.87	77.81
Green Performance Evaluation	3.96	0.82	20.78	79.15
Green Compensation	3.91	0.82	20.95	78.17
Total Green HR Practices Variable	3.91	0.81	20.71	78.11

Source: Prepared by researchers based on SPSS program outputs

Presentation and Analysis of the Dimensions of the Dependent Variable (Hybrid Work Teams)

This variable (hybrid work teams), which included six sub-dimensions at the overall level, achieved an average arithmetic mean of (3.80). This value is good and reflects good consistency and homogeneity in the sample's answers, as it is higher than the hypothetical arithmetic means of (3). The total standard deviation value of the variable reached (0.95), which is good from a statistical point of view, although it was somewhat high, but it is less than the correct one. The coefficient of variation value for the variable's answers reached (25.07), while the relative importance value of the variable reached (75.98). This shows that most of the respondents in the Federal Public Service Council had a clear homogeneity regarding the importance of this variable, and this was clearly reflected in the answer result shown in Table No. (4). The following is an explanation of the dimensions of the variable and its results:

Dimensions of the "Hybrid Work Teams" Variable

Table (4) shows that the "Communication" dimension ranked first, achieving a weighted mean of 3.83. The standard deviation of the dimension recorded a value of 0.96, the coefficient of variation reached 25.2, and its relative importance reached 76.34. The "Trust" dimension ranked second, achieving a statistically good mean, peaking at 3.81. The standard deviation of the dimension recorded a value of 0.9. Although this value is somewhat high, it is less than one. This reflects a degree of homogeneity among the sample members and their agreement on the importance of this dimension. The coefficient of variation reached 23.48, while the relative importance of the dimension recorded a value of 76.46. The dimension of team identity came in last place in terms of ranking at the level of dimensions, as this dimension achieved a good arithmetic mean, but it was not high, reaching its peak of (3.76), while its standard deviation value reached (0.99). This value is somewhat high, as it is close to the correct one, and reflects a kind of heterogeneity in the answers of the Council employees regarding the importance of participation in work, despite the fact that most of their work is assigned to teams for the purpose of completion. The coefficient of variation reached (26.53), and this value is a clear example of the lack of agreement on the importance of participation in their work, while the relative importance of the dimension recorded a value of (75.12).

Table 4. The Weighted Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation, Coefficient of Variation, and Relative Importance of the Hybrid Work Teams Variable and Its Dimensions

Dependent variable Hybrid work teams	Mean	St. dev.	Coefficient of Variation	Relative Importance
Trust	3.81	0.9	23.48	76.46
Communication	3.83	0.96	25.2	76.34
Team Identification	3.76	0.99	26.53	75.12
Total Hybrid Teams Variable	3.80	0.95	25.07	75.98

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the outputs of the SPSS program

Analyzing, Testing, and Interpreting Research Hypotheses

In this section of the research, we analyze and test the results of both the hypotheses of association and influence between the research variables, relying on the results of statistical analysis of the data obtained through the questionnaire distributed at the Federal Public Service Council. We will use a set of important statistical tools, as follows:

Testing the Main and Sub-Hypotheses of the Research

First main hypothesis (H0): There is no statistically significant correlation between green human resource management practices in its dimensions (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, green compensation) and hybrid work teams at The Federal Public Service Council.

Testing the Research Sub-Hypotheses

Upon closer examination of Table 5, it becomes clear that all dimensions of the independent variable (green human resource management practices) achieved statistically significant correlations with the dependent variable (hybrid work teams). All of these relationships were positive and at a significance level of 0.01. The dimension (green polarization) achieved a significant correlation with the variable (hybrid work teams) with a value of 0.497** at a significance level of 0.00, while the dimension (green training) achieved a significant correlation with a value of 0.518**, while the dimension (green performance evaluation) also achieved a significant correlation with a value of 0.723**, while the dimension (green compensation) achieved the highest significant correlation

among all dimensions of the variable with a value of 0.772**. All of these dimensions' relationships were statistically strong at a significance level of 0.00. This reflects a clear interest by the management and employees of the Federal Public Service Council in the dimensions of green human resource management practices, given their significant role and impact in enhancing the performance of hybrid work teams within their organization, which positively impacts their overall performance and enables them to continually develop it to achieve the Council's objectives and move them towards the best. From here, it becomes clear to us that the management of the Federal Public Service Council should focus its efforts more effectively and leverage its capabilities to enable employees to work within multiple teams, given that these teams have the ability to complete the tasks assigned to them at a faster pace than traditional structures in the long term.

Testing the Main Research Hypothesis

Table No. 5 shows that the independent variable, green human resource management practices, achieved a strong significant correlation with the dependent variable (hybrid work teams), at the overall level. The relationship was significant at the statistical significance level 0.00. This relationship is statistically strong, reflecting the extent of the interest of the Federal Public Service Council's management in the research variables, as the correlation coefficient between the two variables had a very high value, reaching **0.753. Based on the results of the statistical analysis between the research variables at the overall level, we reject the first main research hypothesis:

The first main hypothesis (H0): There is no significant, statistically significant correlation between green human resource management practices in its dimensions (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, green compensation) and hybrid work teams at the Federal Public Service Council.

We accept the alternative research hypothesis, which states:

The first main hypothesis (H1): There is a statistically significant correlation between green human resource management practices in their dimensions (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, and green compensation) and hybrid work teams at the Federal Public Service Council.

Table 5. The Correlation between Green Human Resource Management Practices and Their Dimensions in Hybrid Work Teams (n=40)

The Independent Variable and Its Dimensions	Correlation coefficient	sig	Relationship Type	Sample size	Dependent Variable
Green Recruitment	0.497**	0.000	Moral	40	Hybrid Work Teams
Green Training	0.518**	0.000	Moral		
Green Performance Evaluation	0.723**	0.000	Moral		
Green Compensation	0.772**	0.000	Moral		
Green Human Resource Management Practices	0.753**	0.000	Moral		Hybrid Work Teams

Source: Prepared by researchers based on SPSS results

Testing the Research's Main and Sub-Hypotheses

In this section of the research, we will explain in some detail the relationship of influence between the two research variables in general, with reference to the relationship between the dimensions of the independent variable (green human resource management practices) and the dependent variable (hybrid work teams). As shown in Table 6, based on the results obtained from the SPSS statistical program, the second main hypothesis of the research states the following:

The second main hypothesis (H0): There is no significant statistical relationship between green human resource management practices and their dimensions (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, green compensation) and hybrid work teams at the Federal Public Service Council.

The results of the statistical analysis shown in Table 6 show that the calculated F value for the independent variable (green human resource management practices) reached 51.035 at the statistical significance level 0.000. This value is statistically significant, being greater than the tabular F value at the significance level 0.000. This indicates a significant positive effect of the independent variable (green human resource management practices) on the dependent variable (hybrid work teams) at the Federal Public Service Council. Based on the results of the analysis, any change in green human resource management practices will also lead to a significant change in the variable (hybrid work teams), as shown in the following simple linear regression equation

$$\text{Green human resource management practices } 0.823 + 0.286 = (\text{hybrid work teams}) Y$$

The value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) reached 0.567. This value, from a statistical perspective, shows us that the independent variable (human resource management practices) The green value explains 56.7% of the dependent variable, while the resulting beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.823$) indicates that any change in the green human resource management practices variable by one unit will also lead to a change in the hybrid work teams variable by 82.3%. This percentage is considered very high from a statistical perspective. Based on the results of the statistical analysis of the two research variables, we reject the second main research hypothesis, which states:

The second main hypothesis (H0): There is no significant statistical relationship between green human resource management practices in their dimensions (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, green compensation) and hybrid work teams at the Federal Public Service Council.

We accept the alternative research hypothesis, which states:

The second main research hypothesis (H1): There is a statistically significant relationship between green human resource management practices in their dimensions (green recruitment, green training, green performance evaluation, and green compensation) and hybrid work teams at the Federal Public Service Council.

Table 6. The Impact of Green Human Resource Management Practices and Their Dimensions on Hybrid Work Teams (n=40)

The Independent Variable and Its Dimensions	B	A	R ²	R ² Adjusted	F Calculated	Sig	Dependent Variable
Green Recruitment	0.533	1.737	0.247	0.228	12.796	0.001	Hybrid Work Teams
Green Training	0.799	0.691	0.338	0.321	19.884	0.000	
Green Performance Evaluation	0.713	0.780	0.523	0.511	42.831	0.000	
Green Compensation	0.896	0.295	0.596	0.586	57.651	0.000	
Green Human Resource Management Practices	0.823	0.286	0.567	0.556	51.053	0.000	Hybrid Work Teams

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on SPSS results

Discussion

The research focused on identifying the extent to which green human resource management practices impact hybrid work teams at the Federal Public Service Council. Based on the responses of the 40 sample members, the results obtained from the research data showed that human resource management practices, in general, play a significant role in strengthening hybrid work teams. Green compensation had the greatest impact on hybrid work teams, ranking first in terms of its impact on hybrid teams. This reflects the extent to which these teams value the green compensation provided by the Council's management, which further enhances their work performance. Green performance evaluation ranked second in terms of ranking. This is natural, given that employees working in public institutions are evaluated annually by senior management, and the results of the evaluation have implications for several aspects of their work, including promotion, bonuses, and, in some cases, termination of employment due to poor performance compared to the compensation and benefits they receive from the Council's senior management. Green Training came in third place, as expected by the Council's employees, who constantly need training to enhance their skills in both remote and traditional work, thus reducing differences and disparities in opinions when carrying out the tasks and responsibilities entrusted to them. Therefore, without continuous training from senior management, especially with the increasing number of remote work methods, the frequency of errors within these teams will increase, contributing to increased dissatisfaction among them due to some employees' dissatisfaction with overall performance. Green Recruitment came in last place, which is only natural for the Council. With its reputation, standing, and acceptance, it can attract many experts, and employees to work for it more quickly than other institutions.

Conclusions

This study contributed statistically to understanding and analyzing the relationship between green human resource management practices and hybrid work teams. The results of the statistical analysis of the data derived from the questionnaire showed a statistically significant correlation between the two research variables. This indicates a clear interest among decision-makers and council employees in the dimensions of green human resource management practices. This indicates a significant, direct correlation between green human resource management practices and hybrid work teams. The Federal Service Council's implementation of these practices will play a significant role in enhancing the performance of its hybrid work teams. The study results also showed that the "green compensation" dimension statistically achieved the highest impact compared to the other dimensions addressed in the research.

Therefore, council management must strengthen everything related to green compensation by enhancing the rewards granted to employees who contribute to promoting environmental sustainability both inside and outside the council, given its significant impact on enhancing the future standing of the council in the eyes of its customers. Finally, in light of the achieved results, we propose conducting further studies to deepen our understanding of the relationship between strategic green human resource management practices and their role in enhancing the performance of hybrid work teams. This is achieved by using other measures and models that demonstrate their impact in enhancing the performance of hybrid work teams. We also suggest that future researchers add an intervening variable to the study to determine whether its addition will contribute to strengthening the relationship between the two previous variables or whether it will negatively affect them.

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